

 National University of Political Studies and Public Administration
Faculty of Communication and Public Relations

ESDC Course "Strategic Communication in the Context of Security and Defence"

Draft Agenda

Date/Time	Panel	Speakers
Day 1 - Monday, 20/09/2021		
09.00-10.00	Registration	
10.00-10.30	<i>Opening Speeches</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Claudiu Chindriș, Police Academy Alexandru Ioan Cuza - commander/rector 2. Police Chestour Cătălin Andruș, CNAI, Police Academy Alexandru Ioan Cuza & course co-director 3. Cornel Feruța - State Secretary in Romanian ministry of Foreign Affairs 4. Alina Bârgăoanu, professor and dean, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration - College of Communication and Public Relations & course co-director 5. Colonel prof. univ. dr. Doina Mureșan, Director of Romanian National Defence College <p>Moderator: Bogdan Marinescu, CNAI</p>
10.30-10.45	<i>Keynote</i>	Dr. Simion Costea , Eastern Partnership (EaP) - (<i>on-line intervention</i>)
10.45-11.00	<i>Keynote</i>	Ambassador Sorin Ducaru , Director of EU SATCEN and Special Advisor to the Global Commission on Cyberstability (<i>on-line intervention</i>)
11.00 - 11.10	<i>Coffee break</i>	
11.10-12.30	Panel 1: The EU Global Strategy and Its Implementation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sven Biscop – EUISS – (<i>on-line intervention</i>) 2. GI. Mr. (Rez) Mircea Mîndrescu, New Strategy Center, CNAI, ESDC EAB Chair <p>Moderator: Bogdan Marinescu, CNAI</p>
12.30 -13.30	<i>Lunch break</i>	
13.30 -15.00	Panel 2: StratCom – EU vs. NATO Approach	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. GI. Mr. (Rez) Mircea Mîndrescu, New Strategy Center, CNAI, ESDC EAB Chair 2. Col. Valentin Glod, Advisor at Secretariat General of the Romanian Government <p>Moderator: GI. Mr. (Rez) Mircea Mîndrescu, New Strategy Center, CNAI, ESDC EAB Chair</p>
15.00 -15.30	<i>Coffee break</i>	

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15.30-17.00	Panel 3: Leadership and Decision-Making	Simulation. Exercises - Team dynamics. Intro to team assignments Facilitators: 1. Flavia Durach , National University of Political Studies and Public Administration 2. Cătălina Nastasiu , National University of Political Studies and Public Administration
18.00 - 21.00	Welcome cocktail <i>Hosted by CNAI</i>	Marriott Hotel
Day 2 – Tuesday, 21/09/2021		
09.00-10.30	Panel 4: EU Strategic Environment and Decision-Making	1. Gheorghe Savu , National University of Political Studies and Public Administration 2. Kieran Doyle , National University of Ireland, Maynooth & course co-director (on-line intervention) 3. Kai Holst Andersen – EEAS CPCC – strategic communication division - (on-line intervention) - TBC Moderator: Bogdan Marinescu , CNAI
10.30-11.00	<i>Coffee break</i>	
11.00-12.30	Panel 5: StratCom Fundamentals (Persuasion, campaign planning and implementation. Conflict analysis and dialogue)	1. Constantin Spînu , Ministry of National Defence 2. Constantin Bălan , Ministry of National Defence 3. Cristina Ivan , Researcher, Faculty for Intelligence Studies, “Mihai Viteazul” National Intelligence Academy 4. Kieran Doyle , National University of Ireland, Maynooth & course co-director (on-line intervention) Moderator: Cristina Ivan , “Mihai Viteazul” National Intelligence Academy
12.30 -13.30	<i>Lunch break</i>	
13.30-15.00	Panel 6: StratCom Concepts (Communication effects, narrative analysis and development, the role of mass media in the implementation of StratCom priorities)	1. Antonio Momoc , Dean, Faculty of Journalism and Communication Sciences, University of Bucharest 2. Radu Tudor , TV&radio producer and host Moderator: Robert Lupitu , Editor in Chief, Calea Europeană
15.00 -15.30	<i>Coffee break</i>	

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15.30-17.00	Panel 7 – Communicating EU at Home and Abroad	<p>1. Peter Stano - EEAS – HR/VP - Lead Spokesperson for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy - (on- line intervention)</p> <p>2. Flavia Durach, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration</p> <p>3. Mihai Sebe, European Institute of Romania</p> <p>Moderator: Bogdan Marinescu, CNAI</p>
Day 3 – Wednesday, 22/09/2021		
09.00-10.30	Panel 8: Strategy and Crisis Crisis Management and Crisis Communications in the Digital Ecosystem	<p>1. Raed Arafat – State Secretary in Ministry of interior - MAI</p> <p>2. Corina Buzoianu, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration</p> <p>Moderator: Bogdan Marinescu, CNAI</p>
10.30-11.00	<i>Coffee break</i>	
11.00-12.30	Panel 9: Communicating the EU: CSDP Missions and Operations	<p>1. Oliver Hall Allen – EEAS CPCC Head of Communication</p> <p>2. Kieran Doyle, National University of Ireland,</p> <p>3. Corina Buzoianu, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration</p> <p>4. Răzvan Budeanu, expert FRONTEX - TBC</p> <p>Moderator: Bogdan Marinescu, CNAI</p>
12.30 -13.30	<i>Lunch break</i>	
13.30-15.00	Team work - team assignments	<p>Facilitators:</p> <p>1. Flavia Durach, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration</p> <p>2. Cătălina Nastasiu, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration</p>
15.00 - 15.30	<i>Coffee break</i>	
15.30-17.00	Team work - team assignments	<p>Facilitators:</p> <p>1. Flavia Durach, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration</p> <p>2. Cătălina Nastasiu, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration</p>
Day 4 – Thursday, 23/09/2021		
09.00-10.30	Panel 10: The Digital Ecosystem for StratCom/ Mitigating Communication Crisis Process, planning and implementation	<p>1. Lutz Guelner / Martyna BILDZIUKIEWICZ – TBC (on-line intervention)</p> <p>2. Bianca Cheregi & Corina Buzoianu, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration</p> <p>Moderator: Bogdan Marinescu, CNAI</p>

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10.30-11.00	<i>Coffee break</i>	
11.00-12.30	Panel 11: StratCom - Case Studies Mitigating Communication Crises. Crisis Communication Simulation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lutz Guelner / Martyna BILDZIUKIEWICZ – TBC (on-line intervention) 2. Evgenia Karatari - EEAS - EEAS SITROOM Head of Section (<i>on-line intervention</i>) 3. Bianca Cheregi & Corina Buzoianu, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration <p>Moderator: Bogdan Marinescu, CNAI</p>
12.30 -13.30	<i>Lunch break</i>	
13.30-15.00	Panel 12: Disinformation, Fake News, Propaganda	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Evgenia Karatari - EEAS - EEAS SITROOM Head of Section (on-line intervention) 4. Alina Bârgăoanu, professor and dean, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration - College of Communication and Public Relations & course co-director 2. Dan Sultanescu, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration (on-line intervention) 3. Radu Magdin, Smartlink Communications <p>Moderator: Bogdan Marinescu, CNAI</p>
15.00 -15.30	<i>Coffee break</i>	
15.30-17.00	Panel 13: The Role of StratCom in Dealing with Cybersecurity, and Hybrid Threats	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Hanna Smith - Hybrid CoE – (on-line intervention) - TBC 2. Dan Cimpean / Sabin Popescu - CERT-RO-TBC 3. Corina Buzoianu, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration <p>Moderator: Bogdan Marinescu, CNAI</p>
18.00- 21.00	Official Dinner Hosted by CNAI	
Day 5 - Friday, 24/09/2021		
09.00-10.30	RECAP Panel Syndicates Presentation of team assignments	<p>Facilitators:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Flavia Durach, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration 2. Cătălina Nastasiu, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration
10.30-11.00	<i>Coffee break</i>	
11.00-11.40	Future of CSDP	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dirk Dubois – Head of ESDC 2. Moderator: Cătălin Andruș, CNAI, Police Academy Alexandru Ioan Cuza & course co-director
11.40 -12.30	Admin remarks, survey, Handling of Certificates	<p>Closing remarks</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Police Chestour Cătălin Andruș, CNAI, Police Academy Alexandru Ioan Cuza & course co-director 2. Prof. univ.dr. Alina Bârgăoanu, professor and dean, National University of Political Studies and Public

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		<p>Administration - College of Communication and Public Relations & course co-director</p> <p>3. Colonel prof. univ. dr. Doina Mureşan, Head of Romanian National Defence College</p> <p>Admin remarks, survey, Handling of Certificate</p> <p>1. Police Chestour Cătălin Andruş, CNAI, Police Academy Alexandru Ioan Cuza & course co-director</p> <p>2. Prof. univ.dr. Alina Bârgăoanu, professor and dean, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration - College of Communication and Public Relations & course co-director</p> <p>3. Colonel prof. univ. dr. Doina Mureşan, Head of Romanian National Defence College</p> <p>4. Horatius Garban, European Security and Defence College</p>
12.30 -14.00	<i>Lunch break</i>	
14.00 -15.00	Departure of participants	